

CHALLENGES FACED BY UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS IN THE CLASSROOM AND CLINICAL SETTING AT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE INSTITUTES IN KARACHI

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ABSTRACT

Nursing education is generally comprised of theory and practice. Both clinical teaching and learning are essential parts of nursing education.

Objective: The study's objectives are **to assess the challenges faced by undergraduate nursing students in the classroom and clinical environment in public and private institutes in Karachi.**

Methods: This comparative cross-sectional study was carried out in one private and one public sector institution. BS nursing students enrolled in Year -II, Year -III, and Year- IV were included in the study. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$. To compare clinical and institutional challenges faced by undergraduate nursing students in Public and Private Sector Institutions, non-parametric independent samples Mann-Whitney test was used.

Results: Out of 326 participants, there was a slightly higher proportion of females (55.42%) than males (44.38%) at the public sector institutes. 60.2% of students indicated that inadequate skills training at the institute needed to be improved. Moreover, a significant section of 60.2% noted that the curriculum's clinical placement objectives did not align with hospital job responsibilities. Students of the public sector raised more vital concerns regarding the capability of clinical preceptors and the readiness of clinical instructors.

Conclusions: The study determined the problems faced by nursing students in their classroom and clinical settings have a detrimental impact on the learning process.

Keywords : Challenges, undergraduate nursing students, classroom and clinical setting

INTRODUCTION

Nursing education combines theory and practice. Clinical teaching and learning are integral to nursing education, focusing on nursing students' theoretical knowledge and clinical experience [1]. A conducive educational and clinical environment is critical for nursing students to achieve theoretical and clinical competency [2]. A recent research study demonstrated that nursing students faced many challenges due to a lack of knowledge of staff nurses in the clinical setting and a limited understanding of educators in the classroom setting [3]. Furthermore, a current research study established challenges experienced by nursing students include unskilled nursing teachers, inaccessibility of nurse instructors, negative attitude of clinical

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staff, a demotivated environment, scarcity of equipment in the wards, and poor timetables [4]. Current research has documented that having no prior clinical experience, unfamiliar areas, critical patients, and fear of making errors are the challenges that influence students' teaching and learning [2]. It is affirmed by current research that bullying is a rising challenge for nursing students in higher education and clinical environments that has a detrimental effect on their learning [5]. The initial clinical placement in clinical areas has been found challenging as it causes stress and anxiety, which may cause a lack of interest in nursing students [6]. The need for more competent clinical instructors and mentors is challenging in clinical settings that hinder learning [7]. Nursing students encounter considerable challenges persistently in the clinical as well as classroom setting, leading to negative emotions, depressed mood, anger, loss of motivation, and sadness [8]. The conducive learning environment in the school and clinical settings may enhance the student's learning.

Moreover, nursing instructors should be assigned to follow up with students and ensure hands-on practice to learn nursing skills [9]. Hospital clinical nursing faculty can play a pivotal role in guiding students through training [10]. More data is needed regarding the challenges faced by nursing students in classroom teaching and clinical settings in public and private institutions in Pakistan. Hence, the study aimed to assess the **challenges faced by undergraduate nursing students in the classroom and clinical environment** in public and private institutes in Karachi.

Materials and methods

The present comparative cross-sectional study was carried out by one private (Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Ziauddin University, Karachi) and one public sector (Dow Institute of Nursing and Midwifery, Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi) institution in Pakistan. The study lasted two months, from October 2024 to November 2024. The participants were approached using a convenient non-probability sampling method. BS nursing students enrolled in Year -II, Year- III, and Year -IV and willing to participate were included in the study. Written informed consent was taken from all participants before data collection. The questionnaire was explained explicitly to all participants. The confidentiality of the data of participants was assured by assigning code numbers. The sample size was calculated by using "Open Epi" version 3.0. It was calculated by taking the previous study's prevalence of 69.6%. The level of significance was considered as ≤ 0.05 . The estimated sample size is 326 studies for both genders.

Data was collected using adopted and modified tools. It was adopted from a study conducted in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province in Pakistan, and permission was obtained from the principal investigator via email. Some modifications were made after the pilot study. The primary investigator checked the validity and reliability of the tool. As per the calculation scale, the content validity index for clinical and classroom issues is 0.80 and 0.80, respectively. Reliability was found to be 0.82 and 0.85, respectively. The questionnaire was divided into demographic, clinical, and classroom-related issues. The questionnaire comprised a Likert scale with the options strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. A cut-off value of 70% agreement with the participant's opinion was considered a barrier.

Statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version (SPSS version 26.0). For the categorical variable, frequency and percentage were calculated. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$. To compare clinical and institutional challenges perceived by undergraduate nursing students in public and private sector institutions, non-parametric independent samples Mann-Whitney test was used.

Ethical consideration

The Ethical Review Committee of Ziauddin University Faculty of Nursing Ref approved the study protocols. No. 8920724YSNUR dated September 9, 2024.

RESULTS

Table 1 revealed the demographic characteristics of the study participants. At the public sector institutes, there was a slightly higher proportion of females (55.42%) than males (44.38%). On the other hand, the proportion of males was higher in private institutes (55.63%) than that of female students (44.58%).

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Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population (n=326)

Parameter	Public n (%)	Private n (%)	P-Value
Sex			
Male	71 (44.38)	89 (55.63)	
Female	92 (55.42)	74 (44.58)	<.05
Year of Study			
2nd Year	49 (30.06)	44 (26.99)	
3rd Year	52 (31.9)	54 (33.13)	0.1
4th Year	62 (38.04)	65 (39.88)	

Table 2 exhibited challenges public sector student nurses faced in the clinical learning environment. The majority of respondents, 68.1%, strongly agreed or agreed that significant resources were unavailable. Similarly, 60.2% of students pointed out that the information concerning equipment provided by nursing staff needed to be more accurate. Additionally, over 62% of students demonstrated dissatisfaction regarding the hygienic standards in the clinical environment. 60.2% of the respondents agreed that fundamental facilities like drinking water, lifts, wheelchairs, and toilets were often unavailable. 74.2% of the respondents felt that their initial experience was more positive than succeeding clinical placements.

Furthermore, 58.9% of nursing students specified that preceptors did not provide regular supervision at the time of patient care situations. Besides, 52.2% indicated that they were discouraged by hospital staff from seeking guidance. Another issue identified was the non-cooperative behavior of patients' relatives by 51.6% of students. Moreover, anxiety while performing procedures was a prevalent issue among 57% of students. 51.5% of the students indicated that tasks assigned to them do not align with their clinical objectives. Most respondents, 68.7%, also pointed out the inadequacy of learning resources in clinical areas.

Further, 64.4% of students indicated a deficiency of experienced clinical preceptors. A substantial number of respondents (75.5%) found that the clinical environment was non-supportive due to patient workload pressures. Regarding personal protective equipment (PPE), 70.6% of students agreed that PPE was unavailable. In addition, 59.5% of students witnessed a lack of coordination between the college and the hospital.

Table 2: Challenges faced by Public Sector Student Nurses in the Clinical Learning Environment

S. No	Question	SA	A	D	SD
1	Adequate equipment is unavailable	29.4	38.7	27.6	4.3
2	The information provided by the nursing staff for the ward equipment needs to be more accurate.	21.5	27	44.8	6.7
3	The environment is not hygienic	33.7	28.8	31.9	5.5
4	Fundamental facilities (drinking water, lift, wheelchair, and toilets) are not available	30.1	30.1	29.4	10.4
5	The first clinical experience was more positive than the rest of the clinical duration	24.5	49.7	23.3	2.5
6	The preceptor does not supervise regularly during actual patient situations	20.2	38.7	37.4	3.7

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7	During the clinical period, Hospital staff discourages seeking guidance from them	17.8	34.4	43.6	4.3
8	The patient's relatives are non-cooperative	16.6	35	44.2	4.3
9	Have a feeling of anxiety when performing procedure	19.6	37.4	33.1	9.8
10	Students do not assign as per their clinical objective	22.1	29.4	42.3	6.1
11	In clinical areas, the learning resources are inadequate	23.3	45.4	26.4	4.9
12	There is a deficiency of experienced clinical preceptors	29.4	35	30.1	5.5
13	The non-supportive environment due to patient workload in the clinical areas	35.6	39.9	20.2	4.3
14	In clinical areas, inadequate personal protective equipment (PPE) available	27	43.6	23.9	5.5
15	There is a lack of coordination between the college and the hospital	22.1	37.4	31.9	8.6
16	The clinical placement does not help in expanding awareness for nursing role transition	18.9	41.5	35.2	4.4

SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly disagree

Table 3 unveiled the challenges public sector student nurses face in the institutional learning environment. A substantial portion of respondents, 60.1%, expressed that the college needed more information to prepare accurately for clinical work. Likewise, 60.2% of students indicated inadequate skills training at the institute needed to be improved. Moreover, a significant section, 60.2%, noted that the curriculum's clinical placement objectives did not align with hospital job responsibilities. 54% of students were dissatisfied with the evaluation procedure adopted by the instructors. More than half of the students (54%) stated anxiety about starting a clinical practice, whereas 69.9% felt apprehension regarding getting criticism from clinical instructors.

Moreover, 54% of students reported needing more competent clinical preceptors, whereas 53.9% felt their clinical instructors were required to be prepared. 63.2% of the students noted shortages of clinical preceptors, and 52.2% indicated that clinical instructors only visited students occasionally. Moreover, 46% of the students stated that student-instructor ratio was deficient. Regarding workload, 70.6% of students expressed being burdened with written assignments. Moreover, 56.4% voiced that their clinical placements must be more effective in increasing their awareness for future nursing roles.

Table 3: Challenges faced by Public Sector Student Nurses in the Institutional Learning Environment

S.No	Question	SA	A	D	SD
1	Inadequate information from the college to prepare nursing students accurately for clinical work	22.1	38	33.1	6.7
2	Inadequate preparation for skills training at the college for clinical	16	44.2	33.1	6.7
3	Clinical placement objectives of the curriculum not aligned with hospital duties	20.9	39.3	35.6	4.3
4	The clinical instructors evaluate students	18.4	35.6	41.1	4.9

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	fairly				
5	Students are anxious about starting clinical practice	25.8	54	18.4	1.8
6	The students are afraid of criticism from clinical instructors	27.6	42.3	27	3.1
7	Clinical preceptors need to be more competent.	20.2	39.9	36.8	3.1
8	Clinical instructors are not well-prepared	20.2	33.7	42.3	3.7
9	Shortage of clinical preceptors	21.5	41.7	35.6	1.2
10	Clinical instructors did not visit students in clinical areas	20.9	27	42.3	9.8
11	The number of students per clinical instructor is insufficient	0	25.2	46	28.8
12	Students are overloaded with written assignments by the clinical instructors	36.2	34.4	24.5	4.9
13	The clinical placement did not contribute to raising awareness for future nursing roles	23.3	33.1	39.9	3.7
14	Lack of opportunities in hands-on practice	22.1	39.9	34.4	3.7

SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly disagree

Table 4 discloses private-sector student nurses' challenges in the clinical learning environment. A significant concern for the private sector students was the lack of adequate equipment, as 41.7% of students agreed or strongly agreed that essential resources were unavailable. Similarly, 39.9% of students pointed out that the information concerning equipment provided by nursing staff needed to be more accurate. Moreover, 22.7% of students raised concerns regarding the hygiene standards in their clinical environment. Only 20.8 % of the respondents agreed that fundamental facilities like drinking water, lifts, wheelchairs, and toilets were often unavailable.

Similarly, 55.2% of students expressed an opinion that the first clinical experience was more positive than succeeding clinical placements. Besides, 30.7% of students indicated that preceptors did not provide regular supervision during patient care situations.

Moreover, 41.7% confessed that they were discouraged by hospital staff from seeking guidance. Only 31.9% of students indicated the non-cooperative behavior of patients' relatives. Additionally, anxiety during performing procedures was reported by 63.8% of students. 64.6% of the students felt that their assigned tasks needed to align with their clinical objectives. Regarding personal protective equipment (PPE), 53.4% of students indicated that PPE was unavailable. A different lack of coordination between the college and hospital was witnessed by 47.3% of students. Lastly, 52.1% of students confessed that their clinical placement could not help prepare them for future nursing roles.

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Table 04: Challenges by Private Sector Student Nurses in the Clinical Learning Environment

S. No	Question	SA	A	D	SD
1	Adequate equipment is unavailable	13.5	28.2	36.8	21.5
2	The nursing staff provided information for the ward equipment is not accurate	12.3	27.6	41.1	19
3	The environment is not hygienic	8.6	14.1	44.8	32.5
4	Fundamental facilities (drinking water, lift, wheelchair, and toilets) are not available	10.4	10.4	39.9	39.3
5	The first clinical experience was more positive than the rest of the clinical duration	8.6	46.6	30.7	14.1
6	The preceptor does not supervise regularly during actual patient situations	8	22.7	51.5	17.8
7	During the clinical period, Hospital staff discourages seeking guidance from them	13.5	28.2	33.1	25.2
8	The patient's relatives are non-cooperative	9.2	22.7	57.7	10.4
9	Have a feeling of anxiety when performing procedure	15.3	48.5	27	9.2
10	Students do not assign as per their clinical objective.	30.6	34	23.1	12.3
11	In clinical areas, the learning resources are inadequate	11.7	31.3	37.4	19.6
12	There is a deficiency of experienced clinical preceptors	10.4	31.3	41.7	16.6
13	The non-supportive environment due to patient workload in the clinical areas	23.9	31.9	31.3	12.9
14	In clinical areas, inadequate personal protective equipment (PPE) available In clinical areas, insufficient personal protective equipment (PPE) available	17.2	36.2	28.2	18.4
15	There is a lack of coordination between the college and the hospital	20.9	26.4	38	14.7
16	The clinical placement does not help in expanding awareness for nursing role transition	19	33.1	30.1	17.8

SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly disagree

Table 5 depicts the challenges private-sector student nurses face in the institutional learning environment. A moderate portion of respondents (40.1%) expressed that the college furnished insufficient information to prepare accurately for clinical work. Similarly, 46.6% indicated inadequate skills training at the institute needed to be improved. Moreover, most students (57.7%) noted that the curriculum's clinical placement objectives did not align with hospital job responsibilities. Concern regarding the impartiality of instructors was raised by 41.7% of students. Nearly 68% of respondents disclosed feelings of anxiety while starting a clinical practice, whereas 62% felt apprehension regarding getting criticism from clinical instructors. Additionally, 46.6% of students indicated a shortage of competency among their clinical preceptors, whereas 33.2% pointed out that their instructors needed to be prepared. A shortfall of clinical preceptors was noted by 52.1% of students. However, only 30% observed clinical instructors only visited students occasionally. The student-to-instructor ratio was also perceived as inadequate, with 32.5% agreeing that there needed to be more instructors for adequate supervision. Moreover, 32.5% of the students decided that student-instructor ratio was deficient. Regarding workload, 77.9% of students expressed that they were overburdened with written assignments, 47.2% voiced that their clinical placements could increase their awareness of future nursing roles more effectively, and 63.1% of respondents indicated that they felt an inadequate opportunity for hands-on practice.

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Table 5: Challenges by Private Sector Student Nurses in the Institutional Learning Environment

S.No	Question	SA	A	D	SD
1	Inadequate information from the college to prepare nursing students accurately for clinical work	16	25.8	39.3	19
2	Inadequate preparation for skills training at the college for clinical	15.3	31.3	31.9	21.5
3	Clinical placement objectives of the curriculum are not aligned with hospital duties	17.8	39.9	27	15.3
4	The clinical instructors evaluate students unfairly	13.5	28.2	41.1	17.2
5	Students are anxious about starting clinical practice	23.9	44.2	23.3	8.6
6	The students are afraid of criticism from clinical instructors	23.3	38.7	25.2	12.9
7	Clinical preceptors need to be more competent.	13.5	33.1	39.3	14.1
8	Clinical instructors are not well-prepared	11.7	21.5	44.2	22.4 7
9	Shortage of clinical preceptors	18.4	33.7	36.2	11.7
10	Clinical instructors did not visit students in clinical areas	9.8	20.2	42.9	27
11	The number of students per clinical instructor is insufficient	9.8	22.7	44.2	23.3
12	Students are overloaded with written assignments by the clinical instructors	53.4	24.5	12.9	9.2
13	The clinical placement did not contribute to increasing awareness for future nursing roles	20.2	27	39.9	12.9
14	Lack of opportunities in hands-on practice	33.7	29.4	21.5	15.3

SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly disagree

DISCUSSION

The study's objectives are **to assess the challenges faced by undergraduate nursing students in the classroom and clinical environment** in public and private institutes in Karachi. The present study reported that 58.9% of nursing students at public sector institutions specified that preceptors did not provide regular supervision during patient care situations. The study results align with a review article's findings, which disclosed that supervisor nurses offered no support to student nurses in the clinical setting. The study further demonstrated the non-supportive behavior of head nurses towards the nursing students in the clinical areas [11].

In the present study, 70.6% of nursing students stated that hospital management does not provide the necessary equipment for personal safety. This finding is congruent with a qualitative study conducted in Namibia, which explored the lack of logistic facilities for the nurse's safety and medical equipment, compromising the patient's care [12]. In the present study, most respondents noted the need for more learning resources in clinical areas. Similar findings were highlighted in a study in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia [13]. In the current study, more than half of the students, 54%, had anxiety about starting a clinical practice in the clinical setting. Dissimilar findings were demonstrated in a study in Pakistan, which found stress in nursing students during theory classes in classroom teaching [14]. In the present study, concerning challenges faced by nursing students in their clinical areas in private institutions, most nursing students 46.6% indicated a shortage of competency among their clinical preceptors. This study's findings parallel those of a study conducted in Iran, which affirmed that clinical instructors must be more knowledgeable and

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skilled. Furthermore, the clinical instructors do not support and motivate students at clinical placement [11]. The role of the clinical instructor is increasingly crucial for student learning in the clinical setting, and the instructor should have robust skills and knowledge that will help produce competent and skilled student nurses who will take on their essential responsibilities as nurses soon [15]. In the current study, challenges faced by nursing students at private institutions in their clinical areas, nearly 68% of respondents disclosed feelings of anxiety while starting a clinical practice. Similar results were established in a review study that indicated that students are not well prepared for clinical and feel anxiety in private institutions. The study further highlighted that students were anxious and feared working in new wards as preceptors and nurses did not support and guide them [11].

In the present study, 46.6% of students indicated a need for more competency among their clinical preceptors. This finding is congruent with a systematic review and meta-synthesis that demonstrated a lack of knowledge, poor practical skills, lack of confidence, and lack of motivation among clinical instructors [16,17].

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrated the problems faced by nursing students in their classroom and clinical settings have a damaging impact on the learning process. The public and private institutions should devise robust strategies and conducive learning environments to overcome the challenges in classroom teaching and clinical settings for nursing students.

Authors Contribution

Conceptualization: YS

Methodology: YS, B

Formal analysis: YA, YS

Writing, review and editing: YS, YA, B

Conflict of interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest,

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